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Geophysical Mapping And Analysis Of Bathymetric Data For Sustainable Development Of Blue Economy In Parts Of Offshore Western Niger Delta, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The Blue Economy is a recent field of study that encompasses economic activities that depend on the sea, often associated with other economic sectors, including tourism, maritime transport, green energy and fishing. Blue growth supports the sustainable growth of the maritime and marine sectors as the oceans and seas are engines of the global economy and have great potential for growth and innovation. More so, the livelihood of nearly three billion people depends on ocean resources but factors that hinder the progress of the Nigerian Blue Economy are enormous and yet to be addressed. The research was carried out in a qualitative and quantitative approach with high fidelity on-board instrumentation which included global positioning system and gyro compass, side scan sonar imager, sub-bottom profiler, multibeam echo sounder and magnetometer used to obtain the bathymetric data of the study area. After processing and interpreting the data, obtaining charts and maps of the study area, the result consisted basically of three sets of data which were encapsulated in geophysics, geohazards and sedimentology. The research revealed that sediments on the seabed vary from sand through silty to clay. The competent sediments occurred at depths below the seabed at 14.5 m to 15 m. It was concluded that at this depth, which was the competent interface also referred to as the lithified sedimentary sequence within the survey area, vessels could anchor and high stable construction facility could be installed. For the bathymetry, water depth ranged between 6 m to 19 m, 19 m to 21 m, 19 m to 32 m and 6.6 m to 6.0 m respectively for the four fields with a deepening trend from the north to south and topography generally was undulating in the north to gently flat in the south caused by ripple currents and storm processes. Seismic and magnetic anomalies caused by metallic materials occurred in the study area were identified. The sea floor scan also showed existence of genetically related depressions and surrounding rings of sand called pockmarks which vary between 0.9 m to 10.2 m in diameter. Gas charged sediments of 12 m to 18 m thick occurred between the seabed and the lithified bed. Also, pockmarks of 0.9 m to 10.2 m diameter were found in the study area. The major seabed depressions of the survey area were spudcans and pockmarks. This study contributed to knowledge by pointing out safe regions for cost effective development of the offshore province and for reduction of accidents and fatalities. It has also provided guide for further developments, in terms of drilling rigs movement and spudding, wellhead jackets and production platforms installations, vessels navigation and pipe laying operations in the area. Hence the research supported most of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG14 - 'life below water'.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Multibeam Echo Sounder, Blue Economy, Bathymetric Data, Vessels Navigation and Offshore Structures.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of the Blue Economy has gained significant global attention as nations seek to harness the economic potential of ocean and coastal resources while ensuring environmental sustainability. The Blue Economy encompasses various marine-based industries, including fisheries, maritime transport, offshore energy exploration, and coastal tourism, all of which contribute to economic growth, food security, and job creation. In Nigeria, particularly in the offshore region of the Western Niger Delta, the sustainable development of the Blue Economy depends on a thorough understanding of the underwater environment. One of the critical approaches to achieving this understanding is geophysical mapping and bathymetric data analysis. Bathymetry—the study of underwater depth variations and seafloor topography—provides essential insights into the structure and morphology of the seabed. By employing advanced geophysical mapping techniques, such as sonar systems, seismic surveys, and satellite-based remote sensing, researchers and policymakers can acquire high-resolution bathymetric data to support sustainable marine resource management.

The Western Niger Delta, an integral part of Nigeria's offshore region, is rich in hydrocarbon reserves, fisheries, and diverse marine ecosystems. However, unregulated resource exploitation, environmental degradation, and the risks associated with climate change pose significant challenges to the sustainable utilization of these resources. Therefore, the application of bathymetric and geophysical mapping techniques plays a pivotal role in understanding the seafloor's characteristics, assessing potential hazards (e.g., underwater landslides, sediment transport, and erosion), and guiding infrastructure development for offshore industries such as oil and gas exploration, renewable energy projects, and marine transportation. This study focuses on the geophysical mapping and analysis of bathymetric data for the sustainable development of the Blue Economy in parts of offshore Western Niger Delta, Nigeria. By integrating geospatial technologies, oceanographic surveys, and hydrographic data analysis, the research aims to provide a scientific basis for:

- Identifying seabed features and their implications for marine resource exploitation.
- Assessing sediment dynamics and underwater geological hazards.
- Supporting environmental impact assessments for offshore infrastructure development.
- Enhancing marine spatial planning and policy-making for sustainable Blue Economy initiatives.

By leveraging modern geophysical mapping techniques and bathymetric analysis, this study will contribute to a more informed and strategic approach to managing Nigeria's offshore marine resources while promoting economic growth and environmental conservation.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to determine the geophysical mapping and analysis of bathymetric data for sustainable development of blue Economy in parts of offshore western Niger Delta, Nigeria.

Objectives of Study

- To establish comprehensive bathymetric and geophysical data from selected fields of offshore areas in the Western Niger Delta.
- To create detailed bathymetric maps and contour baseline map that illustrate seafloor topography and subsea features of the study area.
- To investigate how detailed bathymetric mapping can positively impact various sectors of the blue economy, including fisheries, oil and gas, tourism, and renewable energy.
- To determine potential seabed geohazards and obstacles for sustainable navigability of the sea vessels in the study area.
- Determine the extent of sediments available for dredging to support subsea infrastructure and installations.
- To provide recommendations for integrating geophysical and bathymetric data into policy frameworks that governs marine resource management and the blue economy.

Area of the Study

The study area is about 25.82 km. It is situated 22.0 kilometers off the coast line from the south western end of Benin river in western Niger Delta of Nigeria. Details of the defining coordinates of the study area were provided in figure I showing Gulf of Guinea and an enlargement showing the study location.

The study area is accessible only by helicopter or sea going vessels. Entry to this offshore environment is generally restricted to only authorized persons or groups.

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area offshore Niger Delta Nigeria

METHOD OF STUDY

Below is a brief description of the captured data interpretation techniques for side scan sonar, echo sounder and sub bottom profiler.

Echo Sounding (ES)

My team at Geomarine systems in May, 2024 determined the sea floor topography by echo sounding techniques, figure 2. A pulsed beam from a transducer returns from the sea floor and is sensed at the surface. By determining the time between the pulse transmission and the receipt of the bottom reflection, dividing the elapsed time by a factor of two and multiplying this feature by the speed of source in water, the depth is determined (Chuku and Ibe 2015). This depth is recorded as one point on the paper chart and many points along a track presented an image of the bottom contour.

Figure 2: Echo Sounder (ES) (Modified after Chuku et al., 2023)

Sub Bottom Profiling (SBP)

A high resolution subsurface profiler which uses wide band frequency modulator (FM) acoustic pulses to investigate sea bed and depth to reflect discontinuities in the near subsurface. The sub bottom profile setup figure 3 is comprised of two transceivers contained within an over side mounted vehicle allowing deployment of the acoustic transducers two meters below the water line, Emery, (1976) and Ibe (1995). The returning signal is processed by the transceiver, which combines the functions of an amplifier, bands pass filter and time varied gain before outputting digital record on ultra- recorder.

Figure 3: Sub Bottom Profiler (SBP) (Modified after Chuku et. al., 2023)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

These consist basically of three sets of data which are encapsulated in geophysics and sedimentology: side scan data, sub bottom data and bathymetric data with respect to sedimentary processes, lithology, seabed topography, subsurface stratigraphy, observed features, environment of deposition and sedimentary structures.

Sedimentology

Seafloor sediments types and distribution of the various fields was studied through the side scan sonar imageries using time varying gain (TVG) of acoustic sound reflectivity and absorption (backscatter principles).

Sea Bed Sedimentary Structures

Basically two bed form types were observed; these include ripples and dunes ripples. These sedimentary features confirm the undulating topographic elements of the sea bed in cross sections within the study area figures 4. and 5. The seabed sedimentary structures within the field has been tabulated in Table 1 below:

The current ripples are located in the north western part while the wave ripples occur in the south western part. The structure and texture of these bed forms clearly divides the shore face profile of the area surveyed into two distinctive grain size provinces: - An upper shore face consisting of fine, sea ward fining sand occurring in water depths of between 5m-31m with current ripple structures; and lower shore face of coarse sand in water depths of above 18m within the limits of study having wavy bed forms that is suggestive of sand waves.

The upper shore face system of wave driven long shore sand flux interacts with coastal boundary of the storm flow field (Whiteman,1982). Sand eroded from the beach and bar by storm passes seaward in intensified rip currents to the zone of friction dominated flow which during storm may take the form of down welling coastal jet.

The wave ripples of the study location must have formed on the transit sand from the beach/ bar erosion unto the shore face where the low wave energy is only able to re-suspend them.

Table 1: Sea Bed Sedimentary Structure for G-Field

Types	Height (m)	Wave length (m)	Remark
Ripples	0.08	0.02-0.8	Straight sinuous or Isolate
Mega ripple	3.64	5.15	Moderately shaped Crest

Figure 4: SSS Data extract showing sand waves, ripples and ribbons in G-Field

Sea Bed Profiles

Seabed profile deals with individual field sediment layers below the seafloor using the sub bottom profiler data; this is to identify the lithified layer that can be designated as competent bed.

Sea Bed Profile Of G-Field

The seismic profiles of the surveyed area suggest the presence of strong stratigraphic interface at 14.5 m to 15.5 m below the seabed figures 6 and 7. The acoustic backscatter properties of this layer indicate that the layer is composed of lithified sediments or calc-arenite formations. The acoustic penetration was found to be limited at the top of this layer. Intermittently occurring weak stratigraphic layers were also observed just below the seabed and the area between seabed and strong stratigraphic interface.

Shallow gas was observed within the seismic profiles of the field. The seismic profile was found to be devoid of any faults till the extent of the acoustic penetration.

Figure 6: SBP Data extract of survey Cross line showing Buried Pipeline and Showing Strong stratigraphic Interface/Lithified Sediments West of G-Field

Figure 7: SBP Data extract of survey Cross line showing two adjacent Buried Pipeline Northward Strong Seismostratigraphic Interface/Lithified Sediments in G- field.

Bathymetry

Bathymetry is the study of underwater depth of ocean floors, lake floors, or river floors. The term "bathymetry" originally referred to the ocean's depth relative to sea level, although it has come to mean "submarine topography," or the depths and shapes of underwater terrain.

Bathymetric Sounding Data of G-Field

Generally, the seabed sloped gently from north towards the south as shown in the contour base map figure 8. Water depth along the pipe route increased gradually from 6 m to 19 m figure 4.27. The range of water depths within each alignment sheet are listed in the Table 2 below.

Table 2: Water Depths within G-FIELD

From Kilometer Pole(KP) to Kilometer Pole(KP)	Water Depth Range (m)
KP 9.50 to KP 12.00	6 -7
KP 12.00 to KP 14.50	7-9
KP 14.50 to KP 16.00	9-10
KP 16.00 to KP 18.50	10-12
KP 18.50 to KP 21.40	12-14

Figure 8: Contour Map showing Water Depths Within G-Field Geophysics

These aspects cover seismic anomalies and magnetic anomalies and were used to handle the installed seabed features within the study area, on and below the seabed using the principles of acoustic reflectivity. In fields O and L, some installed features were observed such as pipelines.

Seismic Anomalies of O-Field

There was a trace of underlying structure on seismic records as shown on contour base map and were detected during the survey, figure 9 details these anomalies are provided in table 3 below.

Table 3: Seismic Anomalies within O-Field.

Anomaly ID Anomaly Position Status of the Existing Pipeline	Northing (m)	Easting (m)	Status with respect to seabed	Position with respect to seabed (m)
SBP040	294013	170593	Exposed above seabed	-0.3
SBP042	294495	170603	Buried below seabed	0.4
SBP043	294045	170603		

Figure 9: contour base map showing Seismic Anomalies within O-Field

Seismic Anomalies of L-Field

The buried pipelines, manifested as parabolas on seismic records, and were detected and is shown on the contour base map, figure 10 during the study and details of these anomalies are provided in table 4 below

Table 4: Seismic Anomalies within the Anchor Clearance Corridor of L-Field

Anomaly ID	EASTING	NORTHING	STATUS WITH RESPECT TO SEABED	POSITION WITH RESPECT TO SEABED (M)
D-SBP001	275724	194039	Buried below seabed	0.7
D-SBP002	275727	194044	Buried below Seabed	1.1
D-SBP003	275716	194056	Buried below seabed	0.5

Figure 10: Seismic Anomalies within the Anchor Clearance Corridor of L-Field

Magnetic Anomalies

The presence of exposed and buried pipelines and other metallic objects in the study area were detected with the magnetometer. These were observed as deviation from the background magnetic value. Their degree of exposure was seen as a result of their strong signal strength. Equally, the range gave an indication of the size of the metallic features detected. The information from the magnetometer was used to complement the information from the Side Scan Sonar and Sub bottom Profiler to ascertain the actual position of all observed metallic features within the study area.

Magnetic Anomalies For G-Field

The details of the magnetic anomalies of the G- anomaly observed within the field as shown in Table 5 below. These anomalies were determined by the survey grids that were running perpendicular to the center grid, figure 11. The localized magnetic anomalies could not be discerned for the survey grid lines

running parallel to the center grid since the magnetic record of these survey lines were found to be dominated by the magnetic field of the Export pipeline figure 11.

Table 5: Description of the Magnetic Anomalies for G-Field

Anomaly ID	Easting (m)	Northing (m)	Amplitude	Description
MA001	292016	170413	184Nt	Negative
MA002	291971	170325	181Nt	Dipole
MA003	291438	169993	121Nt	Dipole
MA004	290662	169332	265nT	Dipole

Figure 11: Contour base map showing description of the Magnetic Anomalies for G-Field

Aspects of Geohazards

These are geological and environmental conditions observed in the study area that have the potential to cause uncontrollable widespread damage or risk, they include pockmarks (fluid escape routes), gas charged sediments, spudcans depressions, debris and other seabed features.

Pockmarks

Pockmarks which are shallow seabed depressions (craters), typically of tens of meters across and a few meters deep, were observed in the study area. They are formed in soft, fine- grained seabed sediments by the escape of fluids (gas or water) into the water column (Chuku et al, 2018). They range in diameter from 0.1m to 45m.

Pockmarks In G-Field

Pockmarks of varied diameters were observed within the field. The pockmarks figure 12 shows the details of the Pockmarks within the G-Field and it may pose threats to the mechanical integrity of the existing pipelines and other would be subsea installations, since they are actually shallow gas vent and it observed in the contour base map, figure 12. The Table 6 below provides the position details of these pockmarks:

Figure 12: SSS Data Extract showing several pockmarks in G-Field
Table 6: Details of the Pockmarks within the G-Field

S/N	EASTING (M)	NORTHING (M)	DIAMETER
1	95638.80	173024.10	0.90
2	94842.50	172363.20	5.20
3	94343.90	172034.00	4.80
4	94283.90	171964.80	7.803.20
	94273.00	171960.00	

Figure 13: Contour base map that shows the Pockmarks within the G-Field

CONCLUSION

The seabed sediments of sand, silt and clay with dominance of high reflective sediments (silt and sand) on the eastern portion with pockets of high reflective sediments implies high wave energy current of turbulence nature exists in the northern portion of the study area and subsea facilities will experience high sediments dislodgment. Seabed facilities will be safer and have consistent burial in areas with low reflective sediments and to avoid subsea structures collapse. The lithified and competent bed occurred 10.5 m -14.5 m below the seabed which was corroborated by the sediment analysis of the well cuttings which show the presence of sandstone at 2 m-6 m which implies that Jackup drilling rigs legs, will have firm spuding on the lithified bed, platforms and jackets will also have firm installations on the lithified bed. The bathymetry of 6 m-32m water depth, with deepening trend of north to south and topography that is undulating in the north to gently flat in the south implies the following: drilling rigs, pipe laying and construction barges, tankers, supply and security boats will navigate 5 m-31 m above seabed, and experience more location-position drifting in the north. Subsea facilities will be emplaced 6 m-32 m below the sea level and will require more support against current in the northern portion of the study area. All the existing pipelines, cables, production platforms and jacket positions were precisely coordinated whether buried or exposed, for future fields development and enhancement. Gas-charged sediments of 12 m-18 m thick occurred between the seabed and the lithified bed. Also, pock marks of 0.9 m-10.2 m diameter were found in the study area. The emplacement of subsea facilities in the areas with gas charged sediments and pockmarks will lead to collapse and failure because they are geohazards that must be avoided. The major seabed depressions of the survey area are spudcans and pockmarks. The spudcan depressions should be avoided to avert failures and collapse of subsea facilities.

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